

VOCTRATOR: AI-Powered Vocabulary Design and Keyword Extraction Tool

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Building and using a common terminology is of great importance for all collaborative work. On the other hand, well implemented tagging of documents by several “orthogonal” vocabularies provides a concise representation of context and topics of a textual data, which facilitates search and retrieval, as well as automated matching of “similar” documents in knowledge management systems. Manually finding relevant keywords for documents is a daunting task, time-consuming and prone to errors. Our “Voctractor” (from “Vocabulary Extractor”) application prototype [L1] addresses this challenge by streamlining both the vocabulary design and the keyword extraction workflow.

Technology

Voctractor is implemented in Python, using the flask framework, and utilises KeyBERT [L2] for keyword extraction. According to the KeyBERT documentation, “KeyBERT is a minimal and easy-to-use keyword extraction technique that leverages BERT embeddings to create keywords and keyphrases that are most similar to a document.” [1]. It calculates cosine similarity between word embeddings and document embeddings, providing a list of suggested keywords. Simple graphical user interface has been implemented in HTML5 (Figure 1).

Functionality

The prototype enables a user to upload one or more documents along with initial list of “stop words” that will be ignored during the keyword extraction process and a list of “candidate” words and phrases. For each uploaded document, the program

generates following three lists: (1) suggested keywords, (2) suggested keyphrases, and (3) suggested keywords and keyphrases from the “candidates” list. The first two lists can contain arbitrary words and phrases that were discovered in the document(s) by KeyBERT, whereas the third is already limited by the controlled vocabulary provided by the user. For each word or phrase in these lists, two buttons are displayed: (1) cross button to reject the word and add it to the “stop words” list, and (2) check button to accept the word and save it in the “accepted” list (Figure 2).

The prototype also presents the document text with all identified keywords/phrases highlighted (Figure 1). This feature empowers users to effortlessly identify where and how often each of the keywords and keyphrases appear in the document, thus enhancing the overall accessibility and usability of the extracted information. To diversify the results, we can use Maximal Margin Relevance (MMR) to create keywords/keyphrases which is also based on cosine similarity [2].

Intended Use

Voctractor application prototype has been designed to aid users in the process of defining controlled vocabularies that are appropriate for use in their knowledge domain and tagging the documents with the terms and phrases from such vocabularies. Recommended method for using the tool is the following:

1. Decide which knowledge domain you wish to address and choose a representative sample of documents to work with.
2. Choose a small number of facets that you wish to generate the (sub-) vocabularies for. For example, for the Climate Change domain, the facets could be: “document type”, “hazards”, “activity domain”, “adaptation type”, “mitigation type”, “location” etc.
3. For each facet, choose a relevant (potentially very long) starting vocabulary. For example, the IPCC dictionary may be a good starting point for the “candidates” list in Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation domain, EU Taxonomy for related activity domains, etc.

Figure 1: KeyBert diagram.

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Suggested Keywords	
forests : 0.5327	X ✓
trees : 0.4912	X ✓
vegetation : 0.4909	X ✓
biodiversity : 0.4238	X ✓
climate : 0.3319	X ✓
tofdry : 0.2385	X ✓
Suggested Key Phrases	
funded tofdry project : 0.3534	X ✓
role in biodiversity : 0.4943	X ✓
forests in global : 0.6499	X ✓
dry land trees : 0.8063	X ✓
trees non forest : 0.5984	X ✓
devoted to forests : 0.6029	X ✓
Keywords from Candidates	
forest : 0.4755	X ✓
ecosystem services : 0.4350	X ✓
biodiversity : 0.4238	X ✓
ecosystem : 0.4179	X ✓
climate change : 0.4075	X ✓
decarbonisation : 0.3897	X ✓
Highlighted Keywords on text	
<small>(Green: Suggested Keywords, Blue: Suggested KeyPhrases, Pink: Candidate Keywords)</small>	
<p>trees outside forests in global drylands tofdry Grant agreement ID: 947757 DOI: 10.3030/947757 Start date: 1 November 2020 End date: 31 October 2025 Funded under: EXCELLENT SCIENCE - European Research Council (ERC) Total cost: € 1 711 487,00 EU contribution: € 1 711 487,00 Coordinated by: KOBNHAVNS UNIVERSITET Denmark Project description: DEENESFRITPL Uncovering the economic and ecological importance of non-forest trees Non-forest trees have been largely overlooked by researchers. In fact, little is known about their density and size, even though they play a crucial role in biodiversity and provide a large variety of ecosystem services. The EU-funded tofdry project will focus on trees in global drylands, aiming to shed light on how human interventions and climate change impact dryland trees as well as how these trees can help to mitigate degradation, climate change and poverty. To find the answers, the project will study the trees on an individual basis, recording their coverage but also their density, crown size, key ecological services and socio-environmental determinants. Satellite imagery and extensive field data will be used together with deep learning techniques to identify objects within imagery. Objective: Drylands cover approximately 85 million km² of the Earth's land surface but their tree and shrub cover is a major unknown in terrestrial research. This is because a large proportion of dry land trees grow isolated without canopy closure and most scientific and non-scientific interest is devoted to forests, while the density and size of trees outside of forests is not well documented. However, these non-forest trees play a crucial role for biodiversity and provide ecosystem services such as carbon storage, food resources, livelihoods and shelter for humans and animals. The limited attention devoted to the quantification of dryland trees leads to an underrepresentation of non-forest trees in development strategies and climate vegetation models, and the economic and ecological importance of non-forest trees is largely unknown at large scale. Through this project I will work towards a wall-to-wall identification of trees in global drylands, and study their ecological services and socio-environmental determinants. The breakthrough is that trees are not assessed as canopy fraction of an area, but as individuals, allowing to identify not only their coverage but also their density, crown size, and key ecological services. I will apply a new generation of satellite imagery at sub-meter resolution and extensive field data in conjunction with fully convolutional neural networks, a deep learning technique being able to identify objects within imagery at an unprecedented accuracy. In doing so, I will lay the groundwork for new insights into the contribution of human agency and climate change to the distribution of dryland trees and their role in mitigating degradation, climate change and poverty.</p>	

Figure 2: Example of Voctractor keyword lists.

- Upload one of the files and run the program to generate the lists, then start selecting the words that you wish to suppress.
- Repeat this several times, first with individual documents, and then by uploading several documents simultaneously. As a rule of thumb, a word that appears in most of the documents is not likely to be very useful for search and matching and probably shouldn't be used in tagging.
- Repeat the process again, this time concentrating on choosing the words that you want to add to facet-specific keyword list.
- Repeat the whole process for each facet, while iteratively refining the facet definitions if necessary. Words previously added to one of the facet-specific vocabularies can (should) be immediately added to the stop word list for other dimensions.

Conclusions and Future Scope

The Voctractor application prototype was developed in the MAIA project, as a tool to help us streamline the process of discovering relevant and useful keywords and keyphrases for annotating the documents pertinent to Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation in a way most useful for later document search and retrieval.

One feature that is currently missing is the fourth list extracting the relevant keywords and keyphrases from the "accepted" list. In addition, some simple way should be designed to test how often the words from each of the faceted dictionaries appear in a larger set of test documents and indicate if there are anomalies such as words appearing in too many or too few documents or discovering correlations between presumably independent facets.

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Links:

- [L1] <https://github.com/ChettakattuA/Voctractor>
- [L2] <https://github.com/MaartenGr/KeyBERT>

References:

- [1] M. Grootendorst, "KeyBERT," <https://maartengr.github.io/KeyBERT/> [online].
- [2] M. Grootendorst, "KeyBERT- Maximum Marginal Reference (MMR)," <https://kwz.me/hAr> [online].

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